

Heat Exchanger Design Considerations Using Carbon Foam Materials

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ABSTRACT

Research efforts have been conducted for the Air Force and Navy to develop improved primary environmental control system (ECS) heat exchangers used on various aircraft platforms. Design conditions for these types of heat exchangers range in heat duties of 50-425 kW and peak operating temperatures of 500-1200 F. These air to air heat exchangers typically involve single pass cross-flow designs currently using a plate-fin configuration. To date, the materials of choice have been metals (aluminum, stainless steels and super alloys) depending on the peak temperatures. However, advances in the processing of carbon materials have improved their cost and have significantly improved their thermal conductivity. Applying carbon materials to advanced heat exchangers will have advantages in both saving weight and improving thermal performance. In particular, the advanced open cell-graphite foams which possess very high thermal conductivity are of significant interest for improved heat exchanger performance and lower mass. Only limited heat transfer and pressure drop characteristic data has been available to date on the specific carbon foams on which to base the thermal design. As part of the development effort fundamental thermal performance testing has been conducted to establish the convective heat transfer and the pressure drop characteristics of several different types of carbon open cell foams. This paper presents the both the heat exchanger thermal design considerations and provides some heat transfer and pressure drop performance data for a open cell foam heat exchanger.

Keywords: Graphitic Foam, Carbon-Carbon, Heat Exchanger, High Thermal Conductivity.

INTRODUCTION

The application of carbon/carbon and graphitic foam materials for aircraft heat exchangers can significantly lower the mass and result in higher thermal performance over the current metallic heat exchangers. The results of two programs that have focused on development of these types of heat exchangers include the primary heat exchangers for the aircraft environmental control systems (ECS for the F/A-18 and V-22. Aircraft ECS primary heat exchangers are used to cool compressor bleed air using ram air as the heat sink. These air-to-air heat exchangers are typically of a plate fin design with a cross flow arrangement, and are constructed of various metals (super alloys, stainless steels, titanium, and aluminum) consistent with their operating temperatures. The primary heat exchanger is also one of the largest and heaviest aircraft heat exchangers on most aircraft. For example, the F/A-18 primary heat exchanger is shown in **Figure 1**, which operates near 1050 °F uses nickel-base alloy parting plates, plenums and headers, with nickel and stainless steel fins. The major component of the heat exchanger is the core (consisting of alternating bleed and ram air layers. The V-22 primary heat exchanger is also a plate fin design, but uses aluminum since it has a lower operating temperature (525 °F). The design data for the primary heat exchangers for the F/A-18 and the V-22 are provided in **Table 1**.

Figure 1. F/A-18E/F Primary Heat Exchanger Manufactured By Hamilton Sundstrand

Table 1 Design Data for the F/A-18 and V-22 Primary Heat Exchangers

<u>Design Conditions</u>	<u>Units</u>	<u>V-22 PHX</u>	<u>F/A-18 PHX</u>
Ram Inlet Temp/Pressure	°F/ psia	215 / 15	196 / 15
Flow rate	Lb/min	72	689
Bleed Inlet Temp/Pressure	°F/ psia	525 / 51	1046 / 133
Flow rate	Lb/min	40	126
Heat Duty	kW	44	424
Effectiveness	%	83	88.3
UA	BTU/hr-F	1600	4760
Materials		Aluminum	Inconel / SS
Thermal Conductivity	W/m-K	190	20 / 15
Core Mass	lbs	15.3	54

Thermal performance and component mass of these heat exchangers can be significantly improved by exploiting the unique material properties of carbon composites and/or graphitic foams. Carbon has a density about two-thirds that of aluminum, and less than a quarter of that of the super alloys typically used for higher temperature heat exchangers. Carbon materials can also withstand high operational temperatures in excess of 2500 °F, much higher than is required for typical aircraft heat exchangers. Carbon composites and graphite foam materials can both provide very favorable thermal conductivities for materials used in the heat exchangers, particularly when compared to metals such as Inconel alloys, steel and titanium.

Oxidation protection is a significant issue for carbon/carbon and graphitic foam heat exchangers. Many existing oxidation protection approaches have been developed for higher temperature applications however; these are not applicable operating temperatures in the 800 to 1200 °F range. Current state-of-the-art approaches involving multi-component coatings appear to offer the best near term solutions, although more research in this area will be required. Carbon and graphitic foam materials have a low, slightly negative coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE), which results in lower heat exchanger distortions and thermally-induced stresses than comparable metal designs. The material offers other benefits such as high corrosion resistance to environments such as salt spray, high temperature non-oxidizing gases.

Figure 2 illustrates the design schematic and photograph for a proto-type carbon composite a plate-fin configuration developed in the Thermal Component Development (TCD) Program funded by the US Air Force Research Laboratory (AFRL), Air Vehicles Directorate. The goal of this program was the design and fabrication of a proto-type light weight carbon/carbon heat exchanger core [Ref. 1, 2]. The proto-type heat exchanger core was identical to the current metallic unit in overall size and configuration, while taking advantage of the unique properties of carbon/carbon composites to demonstrate improved performance and reduced component mass.

The plate fin heat exchanger core illustrated includes the corrugated fins, parting sheets (the flat plates that separate the hot and cold air flow paths) and channel edge closures. The structural and thermal requirements for each part provided a basis on which the composite materials were optimized by the selection of the constituent materials (fiber and matrix), lay-up architecture and processing approaches. This represented one of the first successful designs and demonstrated fabrication of a high performance carbon/carbon heat exchanger. Advances in material characterization, optimized fiber lay-up architectures, plate-fin fabrication, and bonding methods were all successfully demonstrated in this program. In order to achieve the high heat exchanger effectiveness, the ram and bleed side layers required the development of very high fin packing densities (at least 24 fins per inch) and fin heights of approximately 0.25-.4 inches. This was a major fabrication break through with the high stiffness carbon fibers in fabric form being formed without fiber damage in the corrugated fin configuration. The ram and bleed layers were individually fabricated to the appropriate fin heights, integrally bonded to the parting sheets and end closures to form the single ram or bleed layers [3]. The ram and bleed layers were then stacked in the cross-flow pattern and brazed into the overall primary heat exchanger core.

Using the experience and technology developments from the TCD program a program funded by the Navy for development of a carbon/carbon heat exchanger for the primary heat exchanger for the V-22 followed. Goals in this program provided new design approaches, fabrication techniques and validation thermal performance testing. The design data for the current metallic (aluminum) V-22 primary heat exchanger is provided in Table 1. The V-22 primary heat exchanger key differences from the F/A-18 design is operation at lower peak temperatures (reducing the oxidation issues), lower heat duty and lower

bleed operating pressure. The challenges for the V-22 design include reducing the component mass (from the current aluminum design) yet maintaining or improving the heat duty.

One of the unique material properties of the graphitic foam is the very high internal heat transfer surface area associated with the open cell structure. Utilizing graphitic foam for the layers rather than the plate-fin layers was identified as a means of achieving significantly higher internal heat transfer surface area for the same volume. This translates to enhancing the overall heat exchanger thermal performance. The combination of the heat transfer coefficients flowing inside the open cell foam, the high thermal conductivity foam ligaments (providing high fin thermal efficiency) and the high heat transfer surface area all lead to enhanced overall heat exchanger performance. The Technical Discussion Section provides the thermal design consideration and parameters for the V-22 heat exchanger using the graphitic foam.

Figure 2. Primary Heat Exchanger Plate-Fin Core Design and Photograph of the Proto-type Carbon-Carbon Plate/Fin Core Developed in the TCD Program

TECHNICAL DISCUSSION

Graphite foam can be considered as an interconnected network of open cell graphitic ligaments with very high thermal conductivities along the ligaments (up to 4 times better than copper) and can exhibit high bulk thermal conductivities [4]. The pitch-derived graphitic foams utilized here exhibit a spherical morphology and offers bulk high thermal conductivity (on par with aluminum) yet, with a lower density. **Figure 3** shows the spherical cell structure with open, interconnected pores between most of the cells. The bulk thermal conductivity of the graphite foam ranges from 50 to 150 W/m·K and the ligament thermal conductivity from 400 to 1200 W/m·K.

Figure 3. Scanning electron micrographs of the pore structure of the PocoFoam™

Heat exchangers transfer heat from the hot fluid to the cold fluid flowing within the heat exchanger. This involves both convective heat transfer and conduction through the adjoining materials. Improved overall performance for the graphitic foam materials is achieved from a combination of enhanced convective heat transfer and thermal conduction within the heat exchanger structure. The graphitic foam material properties include high thermal conductivity, corrosion resistance, strength, stiffness and low

permeability, high internal surface area and very low bulk density. The potential payoffs in heat exchanger design are higher thermal performance and significant component mass reduction.

The current Navy SBIR program is addressing the development of a carbon composite primary heat exchanger for the V-22 which will provide significantly lower weight and equivalent or higher performance than current state-of-the-art metallic heat exchangers. Extensive heat exchanger design and performance evaluations for various carbon plate fin and foam layer designs have evolved to a design that consists of both plate-fin and graphitic foam layers and designs with foam cores only. **Table 2** provides a performance and design detail comparison for the conventional aluminum and the graphitic foam designs. The heat exchanger geometry parameters (layer thickness, parting plate thickness, number of layers) and the material properties (thermal conductivity, density, foam volume density, foam pore size, ligament thickness) are all optimized to achieve the selected heat exchanger design.

Table 2. V-22 Primary Heat Exchanger Design Comparison

Heat Exchanger		Foam/Design		Al Plate Fin Design	
Thermal	units	Hot-side	Cold-side	Hot-side	Cold-side
T in	°F	525	215	525	215
T out	°F	228	384	270	358
Flow rate	lb/min	34	60	40	72
Heat flow (Q)	Btu/min		2668		2497
Heat Duty	kW		43.4		43.9
Effectiveness			0.96		0.83
Design		Blind Holes	Blind Holes		
Fin/Ligament thickness	in	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.007
Plate thickness	in	0.010	0.010	0.010	0.010
Fins/in or Foam PPI	Number/in	45	45	40	40
Number of layers	Number	16	17	17	18
Layer Thickness	in	0.42	0.29	0.27	0.39
Layer Width	in	3.0	12.0	3.0	12.0
Flow length	in	12.0	3.0	12.0	3.0
Heat Exchanger Height	in		12		12
Layer Mass	lb	5.3	4.3	5.1	7.5
Heat Exchanger Mass	lb		9.6		12.6
Heat Exchanger Volume	in ³		443		436
Heat Transfer					
Reynolds number		413	265	1597	526
Velocity	ft/sec	33	62	61	52
Hydraulic diameter	in	0.015	0.015	0.034	0.034
h: HTC	Btu/hr·ft ² ·°F	253	189	36	23
Fin Thermal efficiency		0.47	0.69	0.95	0.94
Foam/Fin HT area	in ²	42691	33712	13219	20218
Layer UA	Btu/hr·°F	36949	31595	3417	3155
Overall UA	Btu/hr·°F		2881		1563
LMDT	°F		51.4		95.9
Delta P _{ave}	psi	2.06	0.23	1.22	0.13
Materials Design Data					
k: Ligament conductivity	W/m-K	530	530	190	190
k: Bulk conductivity	W/m-K	138	138	53	53

k: Plate conductivity	W/m-K	20	20	190	190
Fin/Foam Density	gm/cm ³	0.63	0.63	0.75	0.75
Parting Sheet Density	gm/cm ³	1.77	1.77	2.69	2.69
Fin/Foam Vol Density	% Vol	26.0%	26.0%	28.0%	28.0%

The foam design represents significant weight savings compared to the current aluminum design resulting in a reduction of the core weight from 12.6 lbs. to 9.6 lbs. In addition, the high thermal conductivity carbon foam designs provides the heat duty for the same core volume with lower ram and bleed air flows. This is a direct consequence of the improved heat exchanger effectiveness. The characteristics of the small open cell carbon foam results in a slightly higher-pressure drop than the plate fin cores. For the current design the foam layers incorporate blind holes to improve the pressure drops in the heat exchanger. The inclusion of the blind holes reduces the effective the flow path and corresponding flow resistance. When blind holes are included the impact on the thermal performance must also be addressed in the design. This includes both the reduction in heat transfer surface area and a reduction in the current flow velocities. All the heat exchanger performance calculations have taken into account these impacts on both thermal and pressure drop analyses. Designs have also been optimized for a combination of the graphitic foam core layers on the bleed-side and carbon-carbon plate fins on the ram-side of the heat exchanger.

Figure 4 illustrates the V-22 primary heat exchanger core for the graphitic foam/plate-fin design that is currently in fabrication. The core is approximately 12 inches by 12 inches by 3 inches and has a heat duty of approximately 44 kW. **Figure 5** provides a photograph for a proto-type quarter section core of the heat exchanger in development and fabricated by Allcomp, Inc. [5]

Figure 4. V-22 Primary ECS Heat Exchanger Design Schematic

Figure 4. V-22 Primary ECS Heat Exchanger Quarter-size Prot-type Core Fabricated by ALLCOMP Inc.

The heat transfer and pressure drop characteristics of the of several single layer foam cores have been established experimentally. **Figure 5** shows some of the various single-layer cores that have been experimentally tested. The single layer test cores include plate-fin layer cores, low bulk density open cell ERG and Ultra-met modified foam cores and the standard and higher density PocoFoam™ (with and without blind holes). The single layer heat transfer and pressure drop performance testing has validated the correlations used in the design and analysis for the full size design. The multi-layer quarter-size design shown in Figure 4 will be tested over a range of operating conditions to develop the overall heat exchanger performance in the final phase of our current Navy program.

CONCLUSIONS

As aircraft systems utilize more and more lightweight composite materials it is especially important to critically evaluate which remaining metallic systems can benefit from the application of new advanced materials. The application of lighter weight and higher thermal conductivity materials coupled with the evolution of improved heat exchanger designs will have a major role in improving overall performance and capability. The graphite foams under development provide several material characteristics (thermal conductivity, density, low CTE, high surface area) that can substantially improve the performance of aircraft heat exchangers. The heat exchanger mass can be reduced and the heat exchanger effectiveness can be improved by utilizing the graphitic foam materials. Designs and fabrication processes for a both carbon/carbon plate-fin and graphitic foam heat exchanger cores have been developed and are being demonstrated in subscale hardware.

Carbon-Carbon Plate Fin
24 fins/inch

Graphitic Open Cell Foam
30 pores/inch

Figure 5. Various Single-layer Cores Tested for the Primary ECS Heat Exchanger Performance

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